

Solving the Fundamental Equation $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y$ in \mathbb{Z}_r

Marco Ripà

2026-01-05

Abstract. In this short note, we provide a compact formula for the smallest (necessarily odd) integer $\bar{\tau}(r) > 1$ such that the fixed-point equation $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y$ admits all solutions arising from the family of equations $y^\tau = y$ with $\tau \geq 2$ in the commutative ring of r -adic integers.

Let $r > 1$ be an integer and consider the radix- r numeral system. Let $p_1, \dots, p_{\omega(r)}$ be the distinct prime divisors of r . Let $r := \prod_{j=1}^{\omega(r)} p_j^{q_j}$, where each q_j is a positive integer, so that $\text{rad}(r) := \prod_{j=1}^{\omega(r)} p_j$ denotes the product of the distinct prime factors of r .

We denote by $\mathbb{Z}_r := \varprojlim_n \frac{\mathbb{Z}}{r^n \mathbb{Z}}$ the commutative ring of r -adic integers. Our aim is to determine the smallest integer $\bar{\tau}(r) > 1$ such that $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y$ has the maximal solution set in \mathbb{Z}_r .

Consider the family of fixed-point equations $y^\tau = y$ for integers $\tau \geq 2$ in the ring \mathbb{Z}_r , and let $\mathcal{S}(r)$ denote the union of their solution sets, namely $\mathcal{S}(r) := \bigcup_{\tau \geq 2} \{y \in \mathbb{Z}_r : y^\tau = y\}$.

The mentioned fixed-point equations originally arose in the course of deriving explicit formulas for the *constant congruence speed* [1] of integer tetration bases in radix- r numeral systems (with r squarefree but non-prime). In particular, the need to understand the stabilization of the solution set of $y^\tau = y$ in \mathbb{Z}_r emerged from the explicit analysis of the cases $y^3 = y$ for $r = 6$ and $y^5 = y$ for $r = 10$, discussed in [2].

Accordingly, let $S(r)$ denote the cardinality of the maximal solution set $\mathcal{S}(r)$ in \mathbb{Z}_r (note that the trivial solutions 0 , 1_r , and -1_r occur among the solutions of $y^\tau = y$ for every odd $\tau > 1$).

In general, the following holds:

$$S(r) = \begin{cases} \text{rad}(r) & \text{if } 2 \nmid r \\ 3 \cdot \text{rad}\left(\frac{r}{2}\right) & \text{if } 2 \mid r \end{cases}. \quad (1)$$

Now, since $\bar{\tau}(r)$ is defined as the smallest integer greater than 1 such that all solutions of $y^\tau = y$ in \mathbb{Z}_r , for $\tau \geq 2$, already occur as solutions of $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y$, it follows that $\{y \in \mathbb{Z}_r : y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y\} = \mathcal{S}(r)$; hence the equation $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y$ has exactly $S(r)$ solutions in \mathbb{Z}_r . The existence of $\bar{\tau}(r)$ follows from the Chinese Remainder Theorem, together with the fact that, for each odd prime divisor p_j of r , the solution set of $y^\tau = y$ in $\mathbb{Z}_{p_j^{q_j}}$ is maximal whenever $\tau \equiv 1 \pmod{p_j - 1}$ (with the case $p_j = 2$ treated separately).

Then, it is not difficult to prove that $\mathcal{S}(r) = \bigcup_{\tau \geq 3, \tau \text{ odd}} \{y \in \mathbb{Z}_r : y^\tau = y\}$, and consequently $2 \nmid \bar{\tau}(r)$ (since $y^\tau = y$ cannot be true for $y = -1_r$ if τ is even).

Finally, we may compactly state that

$$\bar{\tau}(r) = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } \text{rad}(r) = 2 \\ 1 + \text{lcm}\{p_j - 1 : 1 \leq j \leq \omega(r), p_j \neq 2\} & \text{if } \text{rad}(r) \geq 3 \end{cases}. \quad (2)$$

References

- [1] Ripà, M. (2021). The congruence speed formula, *Notes on Number Theory and Discrete Mathematics*, 27(4), 43–61.
- [2] Ripà, M. & Di Pietro, G. (2025). *A compact notation for peculiar properties characterizing integer tetration*, Zenodo (preprint). Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/18012880>.